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NATIONAL LEADER HEYDAR ALIYEV AND HIS URBAN PLANNING HERITAGE

Abstract. Heydar Aliyev, the founder of the modern Azerbaijani state, who devoted his life to the development of the country, a national leader, paid special attention to the modernization and improvement of cities, and the creation of infrastructure. Today, the cities of Azerbaijan are assuming a new modern appearance due to these works. Today, our task is to continue the path laid down by the National leader under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev and make our country even more beautiful.

Key words: Heydar Aliyev, urban planning, architecture, development, heritage.

Introduction. National leader Heydar Alirza oglu ALIYEV is a complex personality and manifested himself in various fields. A huge store of knowledge, a broad outlook and outstanding abilities of the talented politician allowed him to achieve great success, the key to which was patriotism.

When Heydar Aliyev became the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan, our republic began to develop rapidly in all areas, reaching unprecedented economic indicators in a short time since 1969. Azerbaijan became quickly a powerful industrial country from a poorly developed agrarian republic. Heydar Aliyev foresaw the independence of Azerbaijan with his inherent foresight even then, and created a solid foundation for industrial, personnel and architectural potential.

The interpretation of the main material. The 70s-early 80s of the 20th century are associated with a large-scale, hitherto amazing architectural

transformation of Baku and the entire republic. The urban planning and architecture of Azerbaijan of this period is characterized by the extensive development of housing construction in Baku and in other cities of the republic, the construction of large industrial complexes and individual public buildings [3, p. 106]. Special attention was paid to the renewal and modernization of the living environment of historical cities.

Large-scale work on territorial planning of resettlement was carried out throughout the republic. District planning projects for the Absheron industrial hub, the Ganja-Dashkesan industrial district, the Mingachevir and Ali-Bayramli (now Shirvan) industrial hubs determine the prospective growth of existing and the creation of new cities and towns.

Work on the engineering of general plans for the 60 cities of the republic existing by that time was completed in Azerbaijan since 1970 till 1984 (now 79 cities – Agdere-1985, Gubadly-1990, Horadiz-2007, Shahbuz-2007, Khirdalan-2007, Gobustan-2008, Lerik-2008, Samukh-2008, Khizi-2008, Yardimly-2008, Govlar (Tovuz)-2012, Babek-2020).

Landmark buildings in the style of “Soviet modernism” were erected in Baku during this period, which are the legacy of Heydar Aliyev’s era in the full sense of the word, imprinted in time and space. After all, it was on his initiative that epoch-making objects for Azerbaijani architecture were erected in that historical period, which had a significant impact on the entire subsequent development of Baku. I will list the most significant of them: Heydar Aliyev’s Palace (former V. Lenin’s Palace), (fig. 1) was opened on December 14, 1972, architects of which were B. I. Ginzburg, E. R. Melkhimedekov and V. S. Shulgin. It was the largest concert venue in the republic at that time. This building has become a symbol of a new era of Baku architecture – the era of “Soviet modernism”. The Palace, which was built on Heydar Aliyev’s initiative, became the place of his inauguration as the President of independent Azerbaijan twice.

Hotel “Karabakh” – originally called “Tourist”, was built in 1976 by architects V. Shulgin and E. Melkhimedekov. This is the only building of the Soviet period in our country, included in the “World Encyclopedia of Architecture”, which was published in New York as a monument of constructivism in 1978. The project was rewarded the first Le Corbusier Prize in 1979 [3]. (fig 2).

The “Moskva” Hotel was built in 1977 under Academician Mikail Useinov’s project.

A hill, which completed the coastal esplanade of the city in the west - the Bayil slope was intensively built up in Baku in the 1980s. This area has special urban planing and landscape qualities, which consist in a significant steepness of the slope up to 80 meters. It is actively involved in the formation of the sea facade of the city. Landscaping of the territory began in the 1930s under the guidance of architect L.A. Ilyin, the author of the Highland Park. Residential buildings were erected here in the 1970s and 1980s, which shaped the image of the city.

On the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the Azerbaijan Soviet Republic, The Gulustan Palace was built on the complex terrain of the hill in 1980, the architects of which were N.M.Hajibekov and A.Yu.Amirkhanov. The palace also belongs to the iconic buildings of that era. It entered organically the hillside, without merging and at the same time without destroying its relief. The authors of the project used in the architecture of the Palace a single motif for Azerbaijani national architecture – a veranda (eyvan) framed by an arcade, which cantilevered over the walls of the first floor, creates the impression of lightness, an exquisite play of light and shadow. It was here in the Gulustan Palace where the “Contract of the Century” was signed between the Republic of Azerbaijan and an international consortium of oil companies on September 20, 1994.

The 70-80s of the 20th century were a turning point not only for architecture, but also for urban planning in Baku. Without any exaggeration, Heydar Aliyev can be called the founder of a new era of mass housing construction in Azerbaijan and the development of the Baku Metro.

Several more microdistricts and housing settlements were added to the five microdistricts of Baku - Akhmedli, Hovsan, Guneshli, “8th kilometer”, 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th microdistricts in the 70s, clearly engineered many-storeyed buildings of the “Leningrad”, “Kyiv” and “Tashkent” projects, with spacious and bright apartments. They changed, modernizing the architectural image of the capital in a short time. Compact six- and nine-storeyed residential areas were landscaped with wide, green courtyards [3]. (Fig. 3,4).

It should be mentioned big changes in the green building of Baku. On Heydar Aliyev’s initiative, a decision was adopted “On measures for further planting of greenery in Baku and the Absheron Peninsula” by a resolution of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan and the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, which outlined specific ways to expand work on planting of greenery not only in Baku and Absheron, but also in other

cities of Azerbaijan. The construction of large parks and forest parks began, which had great aesthetic and hygienic significance for a city like Baku. A wide network of gardens and parks, a system of windbreaks and boulevards have changed the microclimate of the city and reduced the strength of the northern winds. Great planting work of greenery began to be carried out in various planning areas of cities. The area of green plantings in Baku and other cities increased by more than 3.5 times and in 1984 reached to 11165.7 hectares in the course of the widely developed green building in the 70-80s. The area of public green planting reached 7185.1 hectares, which is about 65% of the total area of green planting of the city[1]. The Nagorny Park, the park named after Shakhriyar, the gardens named after Aliaga Vahid, January 9, the squares named after S. Vurgun, named after M.F. Akhundov, near the monument to Nasimi were updated. New parks were laid out in the central part of the city: Huseyn Javid Park, Zorge Park 1981 [2, p. 78].

Besides Baku, Ganja, Nakhichevan, Sumgayit, Lankaran, Shamakhi, Naftalan were improved and architecturally renovated. New general plans were developed in connection with the development of free territories.

Today, the newest Heydar Aliyev Park Complex, the largest in Azerbaijan and the Caucasus, can be attributed to the wonders of modern Ganja. Its total area is no less than 450 hectares! The complex was created on the basis of the Heydar Aliyev Park, founded in 1979 in the “New Ganja” residential area. The first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Azerbaijan SSR, Heydar Aliyev, planted eastern plane trees – chinara in the park in 1980, which are still growing.

It's no coincidence that Nakhchivan – the city in which the National leader was born and spent his youth is called an open-air museum. Heydar Aliyev's architectural and aesthetic tastes were formed here, under the influence of medieval architectural monuments.

Rapid construction began in Nakhchivan in the mid-70s, which is located on two terraces with a relief difference of 25-30m. Preserving the original architectural and spatial environment of the existing estate building near the city center, it was planned to build new residential buildings with a medium-rise building and stand-alone high rise buildings. A building project was developed for the Yeni Nakhchivan microdistrict along the Nakhchivan river in the eastern part of the city [3, p. 130].

Sumgayit is the industrial center of Transcaucasia, one of the intensively built-up cities of the republic. The construction of the first

microdistricts began since as early as 1961 (architects N. Mammadbayli, V. Khvatkov, V. Kyaziov). Many-storeyed buildings were built on the basis of the products of house-building factories until the mid-1980s. Besides housing, children's institutions, schools, buildings for social services, public institutions were erected. The Sumgayit shopping center, which was built in 1971, distinguished for its expressive architectural appearance, it formed a single harmonious space, turning laconically into the pedestrian areas.

With the restoration of Azerbaijan's independence and Heydar Aliyev's coming to power in 1993, radical changes took place in the social and economic life of the republic. A difficult path of restoration and rebirth from chaos lay ahead. The "Contract of the Century", which was signed in 1994 by the largest oil firms from 8 countries of the world, contributed to the inflow of investments into the republic and the strengthening its economy. As in other areas, serious changes took place in the architecture and construction of Azerbaijan. Architects acquired the opportunity to freely choose the constructive and plastic design of buildings, and a wide range of the latest foreign building and finishing materials opened up before them.

Now, the buildings of foreign embassies, offices of various oil companies, banks, hotels, supermarkets, restaurants, etc. are being built in Baku, the capital of a sovereign state.

Heydar Aliyev, returning to the power of the country in 1993 and having excellent knowledge of its economy, history and culture, human potential, restored the order of the state system and the rule of law with his inherent wisdom and foresight. This served to strengthen the country's image quickly in the international community and ensure its economic and social development.

The first public buildings were built mainly by foreign construction companies. Just like 20 years ago, the buildings under construction were iconic, reflecting a new era, the era of rebirth. The building of the International Bank of Azerbaijan (Turkish architects E. Asadov and F. Bayramoglu, 1995), the 17-storeyed building of the business center "ISR PLAZA", the building of the National Bank (architect V. Mammadov) should be mentioned among them. The central part of the building, which was lined with golden tinted glass, sparkles brightly in the rays of the setting sun, emphasizing the side volumes of the building highlighted by black glass. Photographer F. Khairulin described it figuratively as "the black gold of Azerbaijan" (fig. 5, 6).

Many-storeyed housing construction in Baku and other cities of Azerbaijan has also undergone major changes. All housing construction became commercial. The factory large-panel housing construction was completely suspended. The buildings were built on the basis of a reinforced concrete frame with a monolithic ceiling and a light brick filling. This allowed to carry out free planning of apartments, without endless project approvals [3, p. 216]. First of all, the territories requiring demolition, located near the city center and along its main highways, were built up. The first were 10 and 16-storeyed cooperative buildings of architects which were built on N. Narimanov Avenue, then a group of residential buildings along Nakhchivani Street. Four 10-storeyed single-block residential buildings (architects S.Sultanov, E.Kasimzadeh) were built (architects S. Sultanov, E. Kasimzade), which were completed on the basis of new technologies and with the wide use of glass. These houses, which were built on the basis of a reinforced concrete frame and free planning along Mehdi Husein Street, can be considered a new word in the architecture of housing in Baku.

Construction moved to the city center after 2000. The construction of high-rise buildings in the central parts of historical cities always holds a danger of violating the architectural appearance and originality of the city. The rapid construction of many-storeyed residential buildings is accompanied by a search for architectural design adequate to many-storeyed construction. Glass is widely used in modern architecture as a lighter wall material.

Besides the construction of residential buildings in Baku, restoration work was also carried out. The city began to change. Architectural monuments, gardens and parks of the capital were restored.

The oldest in Baku “Governor’s Garden”, located below the Philharmonic Hall, was reconstructed. The garden, founded at the end of the 19th century, was supplemented with new decorative plantings. Restoration work was also carried out on the Philharmonic building.

The Seaside Park of Baku, where a significant part of the park’s territory was reconstructed and landscaped, was not ignored. Instead of the old stone balustrade protecting the boulevard from the sea, a railing was made of metal handrails. The boulevard is decorated with a cascade of original fountains. The territory of the boulevard is significantly expanding in the eastern and western directions.

Azerbaijan has passed a difficult path to recovery and prosperity during this difficult period. Today Azerbaijan celebrates the 100th anniversary of the Great leader. The democratic, legal and secular state he built during these years is a historical achievement of our people.

Today, our republic is a country that determines the direction of its long-term development strategy. Being in the leading places in the world in terms of economic growth rates, Azerbaijan is known as a country-reformer. New infrastructure is being formed, international airports are being commissioned, thousands of kilometers of roads and modern bridges are being built. In connection with the revival of the historical Silk Road, large-scale strategic projects such as the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway and the construction of a new port in Alat are being implemented.

Great success has been achieved within the framework of the regional development program. An obvious indicator of the scale of achievements in education, health care, culture and social life are hundreds of schools, medical institutions, parks, sports complexes and Olympic centers. Today, our capital is taking on a new look, our cities and regions are getting prettier year by year due to the work on improvement and creation.

Conclusion. Looking at this architectural triumph, I would definitely like to emphasize the continuity of the traditions of creation and say that the work on the transformation of Baku, which was begun by the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, is continued today by his successor President İlham Heydar oğlu Aliyev. Thank to these, the capital now has a whole golden layer of buildings that inseparably associated with Heydar Aliyev's name.

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Samirə Abdullayeva (Azərbaycan)

ÜMUMİLLİ LİDER HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV VƏ ONUN ŞƏHƏRSALMA İRSİ

Müasir Azərbaycan dövlətinin qurucusu, ömrünü ölkənin inkişafına həsr etmiş ümummilli lider Heydər Əliyev şəhərlərin müasirləşdirilməsi və abadlaşdırılmasına, infrastrukturun yaradılmasına xüsusi diqqət yetirmişdir. Məhz bu işlər sayəsində bu gün Azərbaycanın şəhərləri yeni müasir simasını əldə edə bilib. Bu gün bizim vəzifəmiz ümummilli liderin əsasını qoyduğu yolu Prezident İlham Əliyevin rəhbərliyi ilə davam etdirmək, ölkəmizi daha da gözəlləşdirməkdir.

Açar sözlər: Heydər Əliyev, şəhərsalma, memarlıq, inkişaf, irs.

Самира Абдуллаева (Азербайджан)

НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ЛИДЕР ГЕЙДАР АЛИЕВ И ЕГО ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ

Гейдар Алиев – основатель современного Азербайджанского государства, посвятивший свою жизнь развитию страны, общенациональный лидер, уделял особое внимание модернизации и благоустройству городов, созданию инфраструктуры. Благодаря этим работам сегодня города Азербайджана принимают новый современный облик. Сегодня нашей задачей является продолжение заложенного общенациональным лидером пути под руководством президента Ильхама Алиева и сделать нашу страну еще красивей.

Ключевые слова: Гейдар Алиев, градостроительство, архитектура, развитие, наследие.

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Heydar Aliyev's Palace (former V. Lenin's Palace), 1972.

Fig. 2. Hotel "Karabakh" – originally called "Tourist", 1976

Fig. 3. New residential areas of Baku and, 1979.

Fig. 4. Building on Lenin street Sumgayit, 1970.

Fig. 5. Building of the business center "ISRPLAZA".

Fig. 6. The building of the National Bank.